

THE POLITICAL POSITION OF MUHAMMAD RAHIMKHAN (FERUZ) IN THE KHANY OF KHIVA

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Introduction: Feruz, Muhammad Rahim Khan II (1845 - Khiva - 1910) Khan of Khiva (1864-1910); writer and arranger. From the ringer tradition. He learned at the Middle Easterner Muhammad Khan Madrasasiya in Khiva, he gained the study of state and regulation from the well-known mudar of his time, artist and researcher Doi, Yusufkhoja Akhun and others. Ogahi tutored Feruz, showed him the insider facts of verse, history and interpretation.

After the passing of his dad Syed Muhammad Khan (1864), he sat on the lofty position of Khiva. Regarding this occasion, tributes were devoted to Ogahi Feruz. In 1873, the Russian armed force drove by von Kaufman went after Khiva Khanate and caught the principal urban communities and capital of the Khanate. As per the Gandymian Arrangement (August 12, 1873), the Khanate of Khiva became subject to Tsarist Russia. Feruz controlled the Khanate of Khiva for almost 50 years in such troublesome circumstances. Feruz assembled scholarly and imaginative figures to the castle. Affected by Ogahi, Kamil, Tabibi and others, he composed sonnets under the alias (blissful, successful).

Feruz joined incredible significance to artistic work: he created books, composing history, and interpretation. He made an interpretation school in Khorezm. He interpreted the most extraordinary authentic, artistic and logical works of Persian and Arabic writing into Uzbek. During his rule, deals with the historical backdrop of Khorezm were composed by Ogahi and Bayani. Kamil Khorezmi designed melodic documentation for traditional situations with. He laid out a printing house (stone imprinting) in Khiva. "Majmuat ush-shuaro" magazine about writers of Khorezm, works of Alisher Navoi, divans of artists of Khorezm were distributed in it. Through brokers from India, Arabia, Iran, Turkey, Feruz brought special books from abroad to Khorezm and duplicated them in many duplicates, made a rich library of books on history and writing.

Feruz likewise grew such expressions as design, painting, and calligraphy. During this period, artistic expressions of photography and cinematography were made, and it were completed to scene works. In 1871, Feruz fabricated a 2-story Madrasah named after him before the Old Curve. In excess of 30

madrasahs, mosques, minarets, houses were worked under the immediate administration and drive of Feruz. Feruz joined extraordinary significance to crafted by giving water to the land and building gardens. As per his request, an enormous trench was based on the boundary of Kungiroto locale. Right now, this trench is classified "Khan ditch".

Feruz composed verse sonnets in customary classifications of traditional verse. His sonnets are chiefly about affection. Love and dependability structure the philosophical premise of Feruz's work. They are recognized by their musicality, lavishness of pictorial-expressive tones and assortment of shapes. The vast majority of his ghazals were sung by performers and artists in his time. He coordinated his sonnets under the name "Devoni Feruz" (1879). This book was replicated by Muhammad Sharif (1900). Feruz himself replicated 350 Rubai's of Pahlavon Mahmud the hard way and transformed them into a book. Feruz concentrated on Shashmaqom tunes and shaped a maqam group in the royal residence. He created melodies connected with the situation with "Navo", "Dugoh", "Segoh". Feruz was covered in the Syed Mohi Royi Jahan sepulcher in the Syed Mahrujan complex. Duplicates of the assortment of sonnets are kept at the Foundation of Oriental Investigations of the Institute of Studies of Uzbekistan.

The period of Feruz's rule was extremely turbulent, and there was a strong conflict between the khans. There was no unity between the Bukhara Emirate, the Kokan Khanate, and the Khiva Khanate.

Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva are the jewels of the East. For centuries, tourists from all over the world visit the monuments of these cities and admire the mind, art, and culture of our ancestors.

During the Red Empire, the kings from the East were called "ignorant", "ignorant", "bloodthirsty", the saints were called "fraudsters", "liars", Eastern monuments were "relics of antiquity", "religious heresy". to interpret as "when" was a picture. For example, although Khan of Khiva Muhammad Rahim Khan II was a great poet, sensitive composer, patron of creative people, he was branded as a representative of the court feudal-clerical literature, and Feruz's work was neither studied nor promoted.

It is a historical fact that Muhammad Rahim Khan II founded Devon under the pseudonym of Feruz (Feruz - happy, happy) in history, patronized dozens of poets, historians, composers and architects, as well as made a worthy contribution to the development of Khorezm's literary environment and led it.

The great talent Feruz was born in Khiva in 1844. After the death of his father Sayyid Muhammad Khan, Feruz became the owner of the throne. This event dates back to 1863. He was crowned Khan at the age of 16. Historians wrote that the khanate period of Muhammad Rahim Khan II was from 1863 to 1910. He died in 1910.

According to Feruz scholar G. Ismailova, Khiva and its surrounding poets, writers, historians, and musicologists gathered in the palace and created a literary center. Under the direct patronage of Muhammad Rahim Khan, dozens of talented poets, great musicians, calligraphers, and historians have appeared. He collected the poems of every poet and did good deeds, such as creating a divan. led the creation of dozens of collections. "Bayozi musaddasot", "Bayozi mukhamasot", "Bayozi ash'or" are proof of our opinion.

Tabibi's "Majmatush Shuaro" and Bayani's "Shajarai Khorezmshahi" were created under the guidance of Feruz. In "Majmatush Shuaro" samples of the works of about thirty poets gathered in the Feruz Palace were given.

By the middle of the 19th century, there was a special development in the cultural life of Khorezm. Previously destroyed buildings were restored. New irrigation facilities, caravanserais, and about 60 mosques and madrassas were built. Kamil Khorezmi, the owner of a rare talent (Matniyaz), rose from a simple calligrapher to the position of mirzabashi during the reign of Muhammad Rahim Khan. In 1873, he was appointed to the post of devanbegi. "Murabbai Komil" and "Peshravi Feruz" composed by Kamil Khorezmi for "Rost" status are also popular today.

Conclusion

The period of Feruz's rule was extremely turbulent, and there was a strong conflict between the khans. There was no unity between the Bukhara Emirate, the Kokan Khanate, and the Khiva Khanate. Czarist Russia skillfully used these contradictions. Before the occupation of Khiva by the Russians, there was a coup, and his brother Otajon Tora Khan was declared in place of Muhammad Rahim Khan II. After the conquest of Khiza, Kaufman restored Feruz to the throne. Russia's interest in Khiva began during the reign of Peter I. It is known from history that the Bekovich-Cherkassky chief expedition of Peter I was crushed at the threshold of Khiva in 1714-1717, later V.A. Perovsky's expedition (1839-1840) also failed.

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